

A new approach for quantifying the transverse coefficient of thermal expansion in PAN-based carbon fibres at low temperatures via X-ray Diffraction.

Jiraphant Srisuriyachot^a, Wadwan Singhapong^a, Paloma Rodriguez Santana^a,
Carl Sangan^a, Chris Bowen^a, Igor P. Dolbnya^b, Richard Butler^a and Alexander J. G. Lunt^a

^a Materials and Structures Research Centre, University of Bath, Bath, UK

^b Diamond Light Source Ltd, Harwell Science and Innovation Campus, Didcot, UK

24th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM 24)

Baltimore, 4th -8th August 2025

Background

- Thermal expansion mismatch between fibre and matrix
 - Leads to micro-cracking resulting in tank hydrogen leakage
- Conventional thermal analysis method such as dilatometer to measure thermal expansion coefficient
 - Not accurate in the transverse direction of the fibres (5-7 micron)

Schematic of conventional dilatometer in horizontal configuration (Joshya et al, 2008).

Illustration of the TMA set-up for the fibre/film sample (Yang and Thomason, 2013).

Methodology

- Synchrotron experimental setup (X-ray diffraction (XRD) and radiography)
- Dual cryostream to cool sample (open environment)
- Infrared sensors to measure temperature

Schematic of synchrotron setup for this purposed cryogenic testing (Srisuriyachot et al, 2025).

Methodology

- Example of X-ray diffraction pattern of Unidirectional (UD) and Quasi-isotropic (QI) CFRP

XRD pattern of UD shows the two primary PAN-based fibre lattice planes; {002} and {100}.

XRD pattern of QI shows the superposition of the fibre lattice planes in 0, 90 and 45/-45-degree plies.

Methodology

- Microstructure of PAN-based carbon fibres
- Measurement of the change in transverse/radial direction of fibre

The relationship between the XRD pattern and microstructure of the PAN-based carbon fibres. $\Delta\{002\} \approx$ Radial lattice strain and $\Delta\{100\} \approx$ Axial lattice strain (Srisuriyachot et al., 2022).

Experimental results

- Plots of measured fibre lattice strain vs. graphite

Thermal strain in dry fibre closely matches interlayer spacing changes in natural and artificial graphite up to the measured temperature.

The rate of change of the lattice strain varies depending on the initial d-spacing. A larger d-spacing will require less energy to deform the same Δd . The smaller d-spacing is starting to plateau earlier.

Experimental results

- Indirect measurement to obtain coefficient of thermal expansions from three configurations

Experimental results

- Analytical models to workout transverse CTE of fibres

Schapery model (SH)

$$\alpha_{fSH}^{22} = \frac{\alpha_{comp}^{22} - (1 + \nu_m)\alpha_m V_m + \alpha_{comp}^{11}(\nu_m V_m + \nu_f^{12} V_f)}{(1 - \nu_f^{12})V_f}$$

Chamberlain model (CB)

$$\alpha_{fCB}^{22} = \alpha_m + \frac{(\alpha_{comp}^{22} - \alpha_m)[\nu_m(F - 1 + V_m) + (F + V_f) + (E_m/E_f^{11})(1 - \nu_f^{12})(F - 1 + V_m)]}{2V_f}$$

Chamis model (CM)

$$\alpha_{fCM}^{22} = \frac{\alpha_{comp}^{22} - \alpha_m(1 - \sqrt{V_f})(1 + V_f \nu_m \frac{E_f^{11}}{E_m})}{\sqrt{V_f}}$$

comp: composite
f: fibre
m: matrix
F: fibre packing factor

Experimental results

- Plots of measured fibre lattice strain vs. indirect measurement

- Comparison of thermally induced dry fibre lattice strain with bulk CTE, highlighting variability due to model dependent assumptions (Gaitonde and Lawson, 1991).
- SH showed the most discrepancies but matched the reported α_f^{22} ($5.2 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$) at elevated temperature.
- This suggests macroscopic $\alpha_f^{22} \neq$ microscopic α_f^{22} ($26.2 \times 10^{-6} K^{-1}$), likely due to crystalline relaxation from defects (micropores, microcracks, crimps) reducing bulk expansion to $\sim 30\%$ of crystallite deformation.

Experimental results

- 2D fibre lattice strain mapping
- Deconvolution of fibre lattice strain at different fibre orientation

Experimental results

- The average lattice strain was determined and plot against each other
- Thermal induced strain: UD > QI > Dry fibre due to the existing of resin matrix and ply orientation

UD laminate

QI laminate

Finite element results

- Thermal induced strain in fibre compared with microscale FE model
- ~13% error between experimental and FE model at ~200 K

Future work

- Develop a cryostat that is compatible with a beamline in order to reach 20 K or even lower
- Different stacking and fibre volume fraction to fully understand the effect of the fibre orientation

Beryllium dome, I16
Diamond Light Source, UK

Conclusion

- Measurement directly on fibre lattice strain in the transverse direction
- Fibre lattice strain \neq Fibre strain \rightarrow crystalline relaxation
- Deconvolution of fibre lattice strain at different fibre orientation
- Understanding the impact of the existing of resin and stacking sequence
- Accepted by Composites Part B: Engineering

Composites Part B: Engineering

Volume 305, October 2025, 112697

Quantification of the thermal expansion of carbon fibres in CFRP at low temperatures using X-ray diffraction

Jiraphant Srisuriyachot ^a ✉, Wadwan Singhapong ^a, Paloma Rodriguez Santana ^a,
Carl M. Sangan ^b, Chris Bowen ^a, Igor P. Dolbnya ^c, Richard Butler ^a, Alexander J.G. Lunt ^a

Srisuriyachot, J. *et al.* (2025) 'Quantification of the thermal expansion of carbon fibres in CFRP at low temperatures using X-ray diffraction', *Composites Part B: Engineering*, 305, p. 112697. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2025.112697>.

Thank you for your listening

Contact detail:

Jiraphant Srisuriyachot

University of Bath

js2580@bath.ac.uk